

A Study of the Complex Compounds of N-Benzenesulphonyl Glycines with Some Metal Ions : Part (XXIII). Potentiometric Study of *Bis*- N-Benzenesulphonyl-L-Cysteinato Mercury(II)

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Bis-N-Benzenesulphonyl-L-cysteinato mercury (II) viz. $\text{Hg}(\text{RH}_2)_2$ and its disodium salt $\text{Na}_2\text{Hg}(\text{RH})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$ (where $\text{RH}_2 = \text{N-benzenesulphonyl-L-cysteine}$, NBSC) have been isolated. Stepwise acid dissociation constants of $\text{Hg}(\text{RH}_2)_2$ have been determined potentiometrically in 1:1 water-ethanol at a constant ionic strength ($\mu = 0.50$) and at $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$. The values of pK_4^* , pK_3^* , pK_2^* and pK_1^* have been found to be 3.13, 4.19, 10.49 and 11.54 respectively. With a dilute solution of Cu(II), $\text{Hg}(\text{RH}_2)_2$ gives a deep blue colouration in 1:1 aqueous-ethanol at $pH \approx 2.5-3.0$ and a greenish yellow colouration at $pH \approx 9.5-10.0$ indicating some interesting complex formation.

In previous communications^{1,2} potentiometric and rotatometric study of the complex formation of the ligand N-benzenesulphonyl-L-cysteine (NBSC or RH_2) (I), with Zn(II) have been described, when NBSC acted as a tridentate ligand, being biprotic at lower pH values and triprotic at higher pH values.

In the present communication the authors describe the isolation of the complex *bis*-N-benzenesulphonyl-L-cysteinato mercury (II) viz. $\text{Hg}(\text{RH}_2)_2$ and its disodium salt $\text{Na}_2\text{Hg}(\text{RH})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$ when the ligand NBSC has been found to act as a bidentate one. Stepwise acid dissociation of $\text{Hg}(\text{RH}_2)_2$ have been followed potentiometrically in 1:1 water-ethanol maintaining a constant ionic strength ($\mu = 0.50$) at $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$. $\text{Hg}(\text{RH}_2)_2$ has been found to act as a tetrabasic acid and four successive acid dissociation constants have been found out by the method of Irving and Rossotti³.

Experimental

Materials : (a) N-Benzenesulphonyl-L-cysteine (RH_2) was obtained by following the usual procedures^{1,4}.

(b) *Bis*-N-Benzenesulphonyl-L-cysteinato mercury (II) - $\text{Hg}(\text{RH}_2)_2$

About 50 ml of an aqueous solution of 1.5 g of HgCl_2 (1 mole) was added with stirring to 150 ml of a warm solution of 3g of NBSC (2 moles). $\text{Hg}(\text{RH}_2)_2$

separated as a white sticky mass which became granular after half-an-hour. The solid was filtered and washed with water. It was then dissolved in ethanol, norited and crystallized from aqueous ethanol. The white shining crystals of $\text{Hg}(\text{RH}_2)_2$ were collected and dried in a vacuum desiccator over H_2SO_4 and KOH; and found m.p. 187° . The compound on analysis furnished Eqv. wt. 362; Hg, 27.61%; Calc. for $\text{Hg}(\text{RH}_2)_2$: Eqv. wt., 360 (dibasic); Hg, 27.84%. The compound is soluble in ethanol, acetone, dioxan and insoluble in water. A deep blue solution was obtained on adding a dilute solution Cu(II) sulphate to a solution of $\text{Hg}(\text{RH}_2)_2$ in 1:1 aqueous-ethanol at $pH \approx 2.5-3.0$, the colour changed to greenish yellow on raising the $pH \approx 9.5-10.0$. This may probably be due to some remarkable complex formation of $\text{Hg}(\text{RH}_2)_2$ as a ligand with Cu(II). More detailed study is being made on this colour reaction.

(c) *Disodium-bis-N-benzenesulphonyl-L-cysteinato mercury (II)* $\text{Na}_2\text{Hg}(\text{RH})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$

An aqueous suspension of $\text{Hg}(\text{RH}_2)_2$ (1 mole) was treated with an aqueous solution of NaOH (2.1 moles), stirred, when all $\text{Hg}(\text{RH}_2)_2$ passed into solution ($pH \approx 7.5$). The solution was norited, filtered, the filtrate was evaporated to a small volume in a vacuum desiccator over H_2SO_4 and this concentrated solution was treated with an excess of ethanol when a white compound separated. This was filtered, washed with ethanol and finally with a little (1:1) aqueous-ethanol, dried in a vacuum desiccator over H_2SO_4 and KOH. Found: Na, 5.54; Hg, 24.16; loss at 105° , 7.67%; Calc. for $\text{Na}_2\text{Hg}(\text{RH})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$: Na, 5.55; Hg, 24.21; loss at 105° ($\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$), 7.72%. The compound gave a positive iodoform test supporting the presence of $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$.

IR spectra (KBr phase) of $Hg(RH_2)_2$ and $Na_2Hg(RH)_2 \cdot H_2O \cdot C_2H_5OH$ were recorded and tentative assignments⁵ of some important vibrations were made in Table 1, which also contains some such ir data⁶ of RH_3 and KRH_2 for comparison.

The disappearance of S-H stretching frequency at $2597-2532\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in this complex support the formation of Hg-S bonds. The ligand RH_2 and the complex $Hg(RH_2)_2$ showed the C=O stretching band ($1730-1724\text{ cm}^{-1}$) suggesting the presence of -COOH group

Potentiometric Determination of successive acid dissociation constants (k_1^ , k_2^* , k_3^* , and k_4^*) of $Hg(RH_2)_2$:*

Procedure : (i) Potentiometric titrations of 50 ml solutions in 1:1 water ethanol of composition (a) $0.02M\text{ HClO}_4$ and (b) $0.02M\text{ HClO}_4 + 0.005M\text{ Hg(RH}_2)_2$, with $0.12M\text{ NaOH}$ in 1:1 water-ethanol of desired ionic strength were made using a Cambridge pH-Meter (Portable Type) having a glass electrode (1-13 pH range) in conjunction with a saturated calomel electrode connected to the cell by means of an agar $2M\text{-NaNO}_3$

TABLE 1—SOME IR BANDS OF INTEREST AND ALONG WITH THEIR TENTATIVE ASSIGNMENTS

RH_3	Compounds and their i.r. bands in Cm^{-1}			Tentative assignments
	KRH_2	$Hg(RH_2)_2$	$Na_2Hg(RH)_2 \cdot H_2O \cdot C_2H_5OH$	
3257-3175 vs 3077-2857 s	3333-3030m	3250 vs 3070 s sh	3500-3400 s br 3240s br	H-bonded N-H, O-H stretches
2597 m	2532 w	—	—	S-H, stretches
1724 vs	—	1730 vs	—	Due to COOH
—	1575 vs	—	1585 vs	Antisymmetrical COO ⁻ stretches
—	1408 m	—	1410 m	Symmetrical COO ⁻ stretches
1342 vs	1342 vs	1310 vs	1295 m	-SO ₂ N < band II
1163 vs	1163 vs	1155 vs	1145 s	-SO ₂ N < band I

sh=shoulder, vs=very strong, s=strong, m=medium, br=broad, w=weak.

in $Hg(RH_2)_2$ as in RH_2 . This band however disappeared in both the cases on salt formation with consequent appearance of antisymmetric and symmetric COO⁻ bands at $1585-1575\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $1410-1408\text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively. The red shifts of the -SO₂N < band II at 1342 cm^{-1} in complex indicate the formation of Hg-N bonds. Thus the following structure (II) may be tentatively suggested for $Hg(RH_2)_2$:

bridge. The pH-Meter was calibrated with aqueous sodium-hydrogen phthalate and borax buffer solutions with due temperature corrections. pH measurements were made after attainment of equilibrium at the desired temperature ($30 \pm 0.5^\circ$). Ionic strength of the medium was maintained constant throughout by adding requisite amount of $NaClO_4$.

(ii) Titration curves were obtained by plotting the pH-Meter reading (pH) against the volume of alkali added at various stages of the titrations (Fig. 1). The average number (\bar{n}_H) of protons bound to the complex ion $Hg(R)_2^{4-}$ were calculated using the relation⁸

$$n_H = Y - [(v'' - v') (N^\circ + E^\circ) / T_L] / (v^\circ + v')$$

where v° , E° and T_L are the initial volume of the mixtures, initial concentrations of $HClO_4$ and $Hg(RH_2)_2$ respectively, N° is the concentration of the titrant $NaOH$ solution. v' and v'' are the volumes of the titrant alkali required to get the same pH meter readings in the titrations of solutions (a) and

(b) respectively. In the present case $Y=4$, as because four equivalents of alkali were consumed by $\text{Hg}(\text{RH}_2)_2$ for complete neutralisation (Fig. 1). n_H values were plotted against pH meter reading (pH)

Fig. 1. Titration curves —; of (a) 0.02M HClO_4 , (b) 0.025M $\text{HClO}_4 + 0.005\text{M Hg}(\text{RH}_2)_2$, with 0.12M NaOH solution. \bar{n}_H (pH) plot; experimental point; O—O; calculated curve, —, —, —

Results and Discussion

Consumption of four equivalents of alkali by $\text{Hg}(\text{RH}_2)_2$ suggests four successive steps of its acid dissociation as represented by the equilibria (1), (2), (3) and (4).

for which the successive acid dissociation constants are k_4^* , k_3^* , k_2^* and k_1^* respectively. The average number (\bar{n}_H) of protons bound to the complex $\text{Hg}(\text{R})_2^{4-}$ ion is given by the relation (5)

$$\bar{n}_H = \frac{4[\text{Hg}(\text{RH}_2)_2] + 3[\text{Hg}(\text{RH}_2)(\text{RH})^-] + 2[\text{Hg}(\text{RH})_2^{2-}] + [\text{Hg}(\text{RH})(\text{R})^{3-}]}{[\text{Hg}(\text{RH}_2)_2] + [\text{Hg}(\text{RH}_2)(\text{RH})^-] + [\text{Hg}(\text{RH})_2^{2-}] + [\text{Hg}(\text{RH})(\text{R})^{3-}] + [\text{Hg}(\text{R})_2^{4-}]} \quad \dots (5)$$

The \bar{n}_H (pH) plot (Fig. 1) shows that n_H remains practically unchanged (≈ 2) on varying the pH in the region 6-9 which suggests that the most predominant species in solution at this pH range is the complex $\text{Hg}(\text{RH})_2^{2-}$ ion and the second and third acid dissociation steps are independent of each other. There is an appreciable interval of pH between the completion of the second step (2) and the commencement of the third step (3). The plot also shows that there is overlapping of the first step (1) with second step (2) and of the third step (3) with the fourth step (4). Hence the first and

second acid dissociation constants k_4^* and k_3^* respectively were evaluated from graphical solutions (Fig. 2)

Fig. 2. Linear plots for evaluation of k_4^* and k_3^* of $\text{Hg}(\text{RH}_2)_2$ based on equations (6); $\blacksquare-\blacksquare$, $A=5 \times 10^4$, $A'=5 \times 10^{-3}$, (7) $\bullet-\bullet$, $B=2.5 \times 10^8$, $B'=3 \times 10^6$ and of k_3^* and k_1^* based on equations (8), $\odot-\odot$, $C=1 \times 10^{12}$, $C'=1 \times 10^{-10}$; (9) $\square-\square$, $D=1 \times 10^{12}$, $D'=4 \times 10^{12}$.

of the equations

$$[\text{H}^+](4 - \bar{n}_H)/(\bar{n}_H - 3) = k_4^* + k_4^*k_3^*(\bar{n}_H - 2)/(\bar{n}_H - 3)[\text{H}^+] \quad (6)$$

$$[\text{H}^+]^2(4 - \bar{n}_H)/(\bar{n}_H - 2) = k_4^*k_3^* + k_4^*[\text{H}^+](\bar{n}_H - 3)/(\bar{n}_H - 2) \quad (7)$$

and the third and fourth acid dissociation constants k_2^* and k_1^* respectively from graphical solution of the equations

$$[\text{H}^+](2 - n_H)/(n_H - 1) = k_2^* + k_2^*k_1^* n_H/(\bar{n}_H - 1)[\text{H}^+] \quad (8)$$

$$[\text{H}^+]^2(2 - \bar{n}_H)/\bar{n}_H = k_2^*k_1^* + k_2^*[\text{H}^+](\bar{n}_H - 1)/\bar{n}_H \quad (9)$$

all of which can be derived from equation (5) assuming $[\text{Hg}(\text{RH})(\text{R})^{3-}]$ and $[\text{Hg}(\text{R})_2^{4-}]$ negligible at $\text{pH} \leq 6$

values while $[\text{Hg}(\text{RH}_2)_2]$ and $[\text{Hg}(\text{RH}_2)(\text{RH})^-]$ negligible at $\text{pH} \geq 9$ values. The values of pk_4^* , pk_3^* , pk_2^* and pk_1^* have been stated in Table 2 along with standard deviation (σ) calculated by usual procedure⁷. The limits of error⁸ were also found out from a comparison of the experimental \bar{n}_H (pH) plot with a calculated one (Fig. 1). Results are stated in Table 2.

The first two steps of acid dissociation involve the successive proton ionisation of two-COOH groups and the third and fourth steps involve deprotonation of two

TABLE 2—RESULTS OF POTENTIOMETRIC TITRATION OF
 $\text{Hg}(\text{RH}_2)_2$ IN 1 : 1 WATER-ETHANOL ($\mu=0.50$)
 AT $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$

pk_4^*	pk_3^*	pk_2^*	pk_1^*
3.13 ± 0.03	4.19 ± 0.03	10.49 ± 0.03	11.54 ± 0.03

$(\sigma^-) = \pm 0.018$ in the range $(0.1 < \bar{n}_{H_2} < 3.8)$

sulphonimido $-\text{SO}_2\text{NH}-$ groups. It has been found earlier that the acidity of the hydrogen of $-\text{SO}_2\text{NH}-$ group is enhanced when nitrogen of this group coordinates a metal ion⁹. In *bis*-N-benzenesulphonyl glycinate or β -alaninate mercury(II) containing the unit $[\text{HgN}_2\text{O}_2]$ both the imido-hydrogen atoms were lost at low pH values^{10,11}. The low acidity ($pk_2^* = 10.49$, $pk_1^* = 11.54$) of the imido hydrogens in the case of $\text{Hg}(\text{RH}_2)_2$ containing the unit $[\text{Hg S}_2\text{N}_2]$ (structure II) is probably due to the fact that soft Hg(II) forms its best bonds with sulphur which is definitely softer than nitrogen. As a result of this, the bonds between mercury(II) and nitrogen are not as strong as to facilitate easy ionisation of the imido hydrogens as have been found in the other cases⁹⁻¹¹ where the metal ions definitely formed stronger bonds with nitrogen atoms of the $-\text{SO}_2\text{NH}-$ groups.

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